

UNICO
I+D 6G

Definition of 6G manufacturing use cases, and associated requirements and KPIs

Fecha de Publicación: 31/10/2023

6G for Smart Cyber Physical Production Systems of Systems (6GSMART)

Programa de Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G I+D

Financiado por la Unión Europea
NextGenerationEU

GOBIERNO
DE ESPAÑA

Plan de Recuperación,
Transformación
y Resiliencia

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	P1
Líder del PT	Daniel Camps (i2CAT)
Editor Principal	Daniel Camps (i2CAT)
Contribuyentes	Daniel Camps, Estela Carmona, Carmen Delgado, Gianluca Cernigliaro (i2CAT), Miguel Urias, Ivan Boyano (BOSCH), Alicia Gonzalez (INNOVALIA), Toni Ventura (TRIMEK)
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación

PU	Publico
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo

PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

Histórico de versiones del documento				
Versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
V0.1	Daniel Camps	Initial ToC Definition	21/08/2023	
V0.2	Daniel Camps	First draft of section 2	20/09/2023	
V0.3	Carmen Delgado	Update on Section 3.1	27/09/2023	
V0.4	Miguel Urias, Ivan Boyano	Integrated section 3.1	05/10/2023	
V0.5	Alicia Gonzalez, Toni Ventura	Integrated section 3.2	10/10/2023	
V0.6	Daniel Camps	Complete Section 2	28/10/2023	
V0.7	Daniel Camps	Added sections 1 and 4	28/10/2023	
V0.8	Gianluca Cernigliaro	Section 3.3	29/10/2023	

V0.9	Estela Carmona	Review section 3.2	30/10/2023	
V1.0	Daniel Camps	Final editorial review	31/10/2023	

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of Figures.....	5
List of Tables	5
1. Acronyms	6
2. Executive Summary	9
3. Introduction	10
4. State of the Art review on 5G/6G enabled manufacturing use cases	12
5. 6GSMART Reference Use Cases: Requirements, Key enablers and preliminary architecture	20
6. Conclusions	45
7. References	46

List of Figures

Figure 1. 5G-SMART TSN-5G use case in Reutlingen. From [4].....	15
Figure 2. 5GROWTH Connected Worker Remote Operation of Quality Equipment use case. From [6].....	16
Figure 3. MES connected production line use case in 5G-CLARITY. From [9].....	17
Figure 4. AGV high precision localization use case in 5G-CLARITY. From [9]	17
Figure 5. PREDICT-6G virtual PLC use case. From [11].....	18
Figure 6: Current configuration for AI based defect control systems. Same architecture is replicated in each production line.....	21
Figure 7: Shape of EVO Membrane	21
Figure 8: Main SCRAP reasons	22
Figure 9: Other SCRAP reasons.....	22
Figure 10: Layout of the AI vision defect control for the heater membrane production line	22
Figure 11: Envisioned architecture for AI vision defect control use case.....	23
Figure 12. Proposed deployment architecture for UC1 integrating 6GSMART networking enablers.....	27
Figure 13. Resilience in the manufacturing industry.....	29
Figure 14. Resilient and Human Centric approach to digitalization.	30
Figure 15. Traditional alignment of a CMM	30
Figure 16. <i>Vulcan System for Metrological analysis</i>	31
Figure 17. Current Measurement Process.....	32
Figure 18. Metrological Current scenario	32
Figure 19. Future Implementation Diagram	33
Figure 20: Proposed deployment architecture for UC2 integrating 6GSMART cloud continuum and networking enablers.....	38
Figure 21. The past, present and future of video-conferencing. From 2D mosaicking towards virtual meetings, initially with avatars and then with humans represented as volumetric video.....	39
Figure 22. Example usage scenarios of holoportation technology	40
Figure 23. Vision of holographic communications supported by 5G/6G networks.....	41
Figure 24. Envision 6GSMART architecture for UC3.....	44

List of Tables

Table 4-1. 5G-ACIA proposed use cases	12
Table 4-2. Summary of state of the art use cases and requirements.....	19
Table 5-1. UC1 functional and non-functional requirements.....	24
Table 5-2. UC2 functional and non-functional requirements.....	34
Table 5-3. UC3 functional and non-functional requirements.....	41

1. Acronyms

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5 th Generation
5G-ACIA	5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation
5GC	5G Core
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G	6 th Generation
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet Of Things Innovation
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B5G	Beyond 5G
BGP	Border Gateway Protocol
CEI	Cloud-edge-IoT
CNI	Container Network Interface
CORC	Continuum ORChestrator
CPE	Customer Premise Equipment
CPPSoS	Cyber Physical Production Systems of Systems
CPS	Cyber Physical System
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSC	Communication Service Customer
CSP	Communication Service Provider
CU	Centralised Unit
DNS	Domain Name System
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End-to-End
ECN	Edge Compute Network
ECOMP	Enhanced Control, Orchestration, Management and Policy
ECS	Amazon Elastic Container Service
EKS	Kubernetes Service
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EUCEI	EU Cloud Edge IoT
FCAPS	Fault, Configuration, Accounting, Performance, and Security
FENS	Factory Edge Network Service
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GDC	Google Distributed Cloud
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GSMA	GSM (Groupe Spéciale Mobile) Association
GW	Gateway
I4.0	Industry 4.0

ICC	Industrial Cloud Continuum
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LKC	Linux Kernel Containers
LST&P	Large Scale Trials and Pilots
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communication
NF	Network Functions
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
NG-RAN	New Generation Radio Access Network
NOP	Network OPERator
NPN	Non-Public Networks
NSaaS	Network Slicing as a Service
OCM	Open Cloud Mesh
OGC	Ori Global Cloud
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
OP	Operator Platform
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OS	Operating System
OSG	Open-Source Group
OSM	Open-Source MANO
OT	Operational Technology
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
RT	Real-Time
SA	Standalone
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SDO	Standards Developing Organisations
SEP	Service Enablement Platform
SLA	Service Level Agreement

SMF	Session Management Function
SNS JU	Software Networks & Services Joint Undertaking
SSID	Service Set Identifier
TAC	Tracking Area Code
UE	User Equipment
UN	United Nations
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communication
US	United States
VAN	Virtual Application Network
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VM	Virtual Machine
VNS	Virtual Network Services
VPC	Virtual Private Cloud
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WG	Working Group
XR	Extended Reality

2. Executive Summary

This document corresponds to deliverable “*D1.1-Definition of 6G manufacturing use cases, and associated requirements and KPIs*” of subproject 6GSMART-S. In this deliverable we present three manufacturing services that will guide the development of 5G-Advanced and 6G technologies in the 6GSMART project. These services include: i) Scalable real time quality control of production lines using AI vision systems, ii) remote operation of high precision metrology equipment, and iii) the use of holo-portation technologies for remote assistance applications.

For each of our guiding manufacturing services we propose a forward-looking view that defines how 5G-A/6G technologies can be used to enhance these services, and we identify functional and non-functional requirements. We identify how the 5G-A/6G technologies considered in 6GSMART can contribute to each service. Some of the considered technologies include industrial cloud continuum, NaaS APIs, or mechanisms to enhance uplink data rates.

3. Introduction

6GSMART is an R&D project under the Spanish UNICO framework that investigates how 5G technology needs to evolve to address the unique needs of presented by Operational Technologies (OT).

To identify the 5G/6G technologies that can best address OT requirements, 6GSMART adopts a combined top-down and bottom-up methodology:

- Top-down approach: 6GSMART will build on three reference manufacturing use cases, which push the boundaries of current network capabilities and will allow the consortium to derive requirements for future 6G networks.
- Bottom-Up approach: 6GSMART will carry out fundamental research on networking to identify technologies that can contribute to enhance performance of OT applications.

To this end, the overall 6GSMART project is organized in 4 separate sub-projects:

- 6GSMART-S, where “S” stands for *Services*. The goal of this subproject is to design and develop the three reference 6GSMART OT use cases that will guide the development of networking technologies.
- 6GSMART-EZ, where “EZ” stands for *Extreme KPIs* and *Zero Touch Automation*. The goal of this subproject is to develop networking enablers that push forward 5G KPIs in terms of throughput, latency and localization, as well as management enablers that simplify the operations of 5G/6G networks in manufacturing environments.
- 6GSMART-ICC, where “ICC” stands for *Industrial Cloud Continuum*. The goal of this subproject is to develop cloud continuum enablers applied to manufacturing environments.
- 6GSMART-EXP, where “EXP” stands for *Experimentation*. The goal of this subproject is to develop demonstrators that bring together the services developed in 6GSMART-S with the enablers developed in 6GSMART-EZ and 6GSMART-ICC.

This document corresponds to deliverable “*DI.1-Definition of 6G manufacturing use cases, and associated requirements and KPIs*” of subproject 6GSMART-S, which introduces the three driving 6GSMART manufacturing use cases, while deriving functional and non-functional requirements. This document will be used as reference for the developments carried out in all the other subprojects.

3.1. Structure of this deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 provides a review of the state of the art in terms of manufacturing use cases that have been identified by industrial bodies like 5G-ACIA, by Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) like 3GPP, and by research projects belonging to the 5GPPP program.
- Section 3 introduces the three reference manufacturing use cases in 6GSMART, namely: UC1 related to AI vision applied to real time quality control, UC2 related

to remote operation of high precision metrology, and UC3 related to use of holoportation technology for remote assistance in manufacturing environments.

- Section 4 summarizes and concludes this document.

4. State of the Art review on 5G/6G enabled manufacturing use cases

In this section we survey the state of the art on industrial use cases for 5G and 6G networks, focusing on 5G-ACIA, 3GPP and a set of selected 5GPPP projects.

4.1. 5G-ACIA proposed Use Cases

5G-ACIA is an industry interest group composed of major OT and IT groups that has the goal of promoting the adoption of 5G technologies in the manufacturing domain. 5G-ACIA is also registered as a Market Representation Partner (MRP) representing the industrial automation vertical within 3GPP.

In [1], 5G-ACIA defined a set of reference industrial use case categories that were used to elicit requirements and to influence the standardization process in 3GPP. The following table depicts the main use case categories identified by 5G-ACIA.

Table 4-1. 5G-ACIA proposed use cases

Use Case Category	Description
Connectivity on the factory floor	Includes any robot/sensor/actuator on the factory floor that needs to be connected. A closed loop automation enabled by the cellular connectivity is also envisioned. <u>Examples:</u> Safety light curtain, Machine layout planning
Seamless integration of wired and wireless components for motion control	Not all devices will be connected wirelessly, so wired-wireless integration is essential on the factory floor. <u>Examples:</u> body chassis marriage in automobile manufacturing
Local control-to-control communications	Control-to-control refers to controllers (e.g. PLCs) that need to coordinate with each other. Local refers to these controllers being physically close to each other, e.g. multiple machines within the same production building. Communication in these cases is often not based on IP. <u>Examples:</u> shuttles in a packaging machine, collaborative component handling.
Remote control-to-control communications	Refers to communication between controllers in remote locations. This communication is assumed to be seldom, unlike local control-to-control communication. <u>Examples:</u> remotely controlled PCB assembly lines
Mobile robots and AGVs	Includes any robots or vehicles that operate autonomously on the factory floor. <u>Examples:</u> mobile robots, AGVs in a chemical plant

Closed-loop control for process automation	Closed loop between sensors, actuators and control units, which require fast and reliable communications. <u>Examples:</u> controlled conditions in a chemical reactor
Remote monitoring for process automation	Includes communications for observation, diagnosis or monitoring, and may entail use of public networks. <u>Example:</u> Oil&gas fields

Based on the aforementioned use case categories, 5G-ACIA elicits a set of high-level requirements in terms of: i) Reliability and availability, ii) Security, iii) Latency, iv) Diagnostics and v) Network isolation. The interested reader is referred to [1] for a detailed discussion on these requirements.

4.2. 3GPP industrial use cases

In TS 22.104 [2] 3GPP identifies requirements for cyber-physical control applications, which includes factories of the future. In this document 3GPP identifies three main communication patterns stemming from these systems, namely: i) deterministic periodic communications with stringent requirements on timeliness of the transmission, ii) deterministic aperiodic communication, which also have timeliness requirement, but its generation cannot be predicted, and iii) non-deterministic communication, which would include all other traffic types.

TS 22.104 then identifies, for each communication pattern a set of relevant use cases, and for each case defines a traffic pattern, which we briefly summarize here. The interested reader is referred to TS 22.104 [2] for a complete description of the identified traffic patterns.

- Periodic deterministic communication service:
 - o Example use cases:
 - Motion Control
 - Control to Control
 - Mobile Robots
 - Mobile Control panels
 - o Exemplary parameters and values:
 - Message Size (Bytes): 50 - 1000
 - Transfer interval: 1ms – 100 ms
 - Survival time: $n \cdot \text{Transfer Interval}$, with $n=1$ or 2
- Aperiodic deterministic communication:
 - o Example use cases:
 - Augmented Reality
 - Mobile robots – video streaming
 - o Exemplary parameters and values:
 - Max allowed end-to-end latency: 1 ms – 50 ms
 - Service bit rate: 10 Mbps – 500 Mbps
- Non-deterministic communication:
 - o Example use cases:
 - Motion Control – software updates
 - Mobile robots - real time video streaming
 - o Exemplary parameters and values:
 - Service bit rates: 1 Mbps – 10 Mbps in UL/DL
 - Number of UEs: < 100

4.3. Review on 5GPPP manufacturing use cases

The 5GPPP and SNS initiatives are public private partnerships between the European Commission and the ICT industry to foster the development of the 5G and 6G technologies respectively. These initiatives have funded several projects that have executed numerous pilots to integrate 5G into vertical services. In this section we review the main use cases of the 5GPPP and SNS projects that have focused on manufacturing and Industry 4.0.

4.3.1. 5G-SMART Project

5G-SMART [3], which finished in 2020, was a flagship 5GPPP project studying the application of 5G into manufacturing use cases. The project was organized around three main trials in Kista, Aachen and Reutlingen, each developing complementary use cases.

4.3.1.1. Kista Use Cases

The first use case developed in Kista focused on collaboration between mobile robots, stationary robots and human workers. The use case featured image processing and motion planning functions deployed in a factory edge, which could understand the environment and send command instructions towards the robots to avoid collisions. For this use case, 5G-SMART reports average data rate requirements per robot of up to 2 Mbps in DL and UL, with transfer intervals between 5 and 40 ms [4].

A second use case in Kista focuses on the visualization of real time information generated by mobile robots into an AR headset worn by a factory worker. Like the robots, the AR headset is 5G connected and all processing functions are located in the factory edge. For this use case a communication lag of 100-200 ms is identified as maximum latency between data generated by the robots and the data being displayed in the AR headset.

4.3.1.2. Aachen Use Cases

In the Aachen site two use cases are developed. First, a use case about a 5G enabled wireless acoustic workpiece monitoring. Acoustic monitoring is used for predictive monitoring of cutting tools. In this use case an acoustic sensor positioned next to the cutting machinery is provided with a 5G modem. The sensor streams the acoustic samples to a processing function located in the factory edge computing. Deterministic latency is required to be able to react to a critical event, such as tool breakage. A minimum uplink communication data rate of 8 Mbps and a latency below 10 ms are identified for this use case.

The second use case consists of the development of a 5G enabled multi-sensor platform measuring variables such as temperature, pressure, vibration, acceleration. Multiple (>10) multi-sensor platforms are collocated with machines in the factory floor for monitoring purposes. The data generated by the multi-sensor platforms is then streamed to a digital twin function that is deployed in the factory edge. The digital twin function is then able to issue configuration instructions against the machines monitored by the multi-sensor

platform, although this last communication is implemented via Ethernet (not 5G). A maximum uplink latency of 10 ms is identified as requirement for this use case.

4.3.1.3. Reutlingen Use Cases

In the Reutlingen trial, 5G-SMART developed two additional use cases. The first use case deals with cloud-based mobile robotics, where the control functions of 5G connected Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) are partially offloaded to the local edge resources in the factory. To realize this use case, fleet control, trajectory control, SLAM functions and safety functions need to be centralized in the factory edge and interact with the HW control modules available in the AGV. For this use case, service data rates between each AGV and the control functions in the factory edge are identified to be < 10 Mbps in DL and 1-100 Mbps in UL (depending on the degree of edge offloading), with transfer intervals between 10 ms and 100 ms.

The second use case in Reutlingen features the integration of an IEEE 802.1 TSN network with a private 5G system, focusing into controller-to-controller (C2C) communications required for example in industrial printers or packaging systems, where different units are controlled by dedicated PLCs and communication between PLCs is required. Figure 1 depicts the architecture envisioned for this use case. For this use case, the C2C traffic consists of messages in the order of 500 B with a transfer interval between 4 ms and 10 ms. Deterministic communication needs to be ensured.

Figure 1. 5G-SMART TSN-5G use case in Reutlingen. From [4]

4.3.2. 5GROWTH Project

5GROWTH [5] was a 5GPPP phase 3 project focusing on validation of 5G technologies in vertical industries. 5GROWTH included an industry 4.0 use case with the goal of enabling remote operation of metrology machinery, which is used for quality assurance in manufacturing.

Figure 2 depicts a Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM) used to scan a manufactured part and to compare it against a pre-defined specification, being able to detect manufacturing defects with a micro-meter resolution. To operate the CMM an edge device, referred to as M3BOX, is currently being used, which allows a technician to

control the CMM in the process of scanning the manufactured part. Currently, the technician needs to be located next to the M3BOX to operate the CMM. The goal of this use case was therefore to enable remote operation of the CMM, by separating the remote-control platform from the M3BOX, and connecting both using a public or private 5G network.

In [6] the main network requirements are identified for this use case, which include: i) 99,99% availability, ii) security and e2e encryption, iii) 100 Mbps service rate in UL for video cameras used to stream CMM status to the remote operation platform, iv) <400Kbps service rate in DL for the control traffic between the remote operation platform and the M3BOX.

This use case will serve as basis for UC2 in 6GSMART, which is described in Section 3.1.

Figure 2. 5GROWTH Connected Worker Remote Operation of Quality Equipment use case. From [6]

4.3.3. 5G-CLARITY Project

5G-CLARITY [7] is a 5GPPP project that finished in 2023, which proposed the design of private 5G networks that integrate three wireless access technologies, namely 5GNR, Wi-Fi and LiFi (802.11bb-based). 5G-CLARITY defined an architecture [8] that aggregated these three access networks using a multi-connectivity framework based on the Adaptive Traffic Steering, Switching and Splitting (ATSSS) functionality defined by 3GPP in Release 16. 5G-CLARITY developed an ATSSS implementation based on Multi-Path TCP (MPTCP) that was demonstrated in a factory environment provided by BOSCH in Aranjuez. In addition to multi-connectivity, 5G-CLARITY also developed mechanisms for high-precision localization that were also validated in the Aranjuez factory environment.

5G-CLARITY demonstrated two manufacturing use cases. First, a use case about connecting production lines to a Manufacturing Execution Server (MES) using 5G, and a second use case about high precision localization of AGVs using RF based localization. Figure 3 depicts the vision of a wirelessly connected production line proposed by 5G-CLARITY, where the head of line switch present in current production lines is replaced

by a 5G-CLARITY CPE that includes WiFi, 5G NR and LiFi interfaces. By means of packet duplication through the different networks, 5G-CLARITY achieves round-trip latencies between the PLCs and the MES in the technical room below 10 ms, even when the wireless access networks have load utilization levels as high as 80%.

Figure 3. MES connected production line use case in 5G-CLARITY. From [9]

Figure 4 depicts the AGV high precision localization use case demonstrated in BOSCH Aranjuez. High precision localization is required to optimize the AGV routes and maximize the storage space in the factory floor. To implement the use case, Sub6 and mm-wave radio anchors were deployed at the factory floor, and SDR receivers were mounted on a trolley pulled by the AGV. Sub-meter localization accuracies were achieved with both radio technologies under static conditions, as illustrated in the right-hand side of Figure 4.

Figure 4. AGV high precision localization use case in 5G-CLARITY. From [9]

4.3.4. PREDICT-6G Project

PREDICT-6G [10] is an SNS project started in 2023 that aims to develop a novel architecture to provide deterministic networking services over multi-domain and multi-technology networks. The project considers two main use cases in the area of industry 4.0 and critical communications.

4.3.4.1. Use Case 1: Smart manufacturing (virtual PLC)

In current factories, manufacturing processes are implemented through production lines, whereby a group of sensors and actuators are controlled by a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC). The sensors and actuators are connected to the PLC using a field bus technology, which is typically a derivative of Ethernet. Then, PLCs are connected to Manufacturing Execution Servers (MES) installed in a technical room, also using Ethernet connectivity. While being very reliable, the current system lacks flexibility and hinders the reconfigurability of production lines, which is required to achieve agile production environments. The right side of Figure 5 depicts the smart factory vision put forward by the PREDICT-6G project, where sensors and actuators are connected wirelessly to an edge compute infrastructure hosted in the factory premises, which can then implement the PLC function as a software function, packaged for example in a virtual machine.

To implement this use case, PREDICT-6G identifies a PLC cycle scan of 10 ms, which results in a maximum latency bound of 5 ms and 2 ms of jitter between the sensors and actuators and the virtual PLC deployed in the factory edge.

Figure 5. PREDICT-6G virtual PLC use case. From [11].

4.3.4.2. Use Case 2: Critical communications.

The second use case considered in PREDICT-6G focuses on critical communications, understood as communication services that cannot tolerate failures. An example considered is that of robots connected to a cloud compute host, whereby sensors in the robots generate real time analytics, which are processed in the cloud host, which then generates actuation commands down to the robot.

A representative traffic pattern for this type of communications, consists of sensors generating periodic batches of data in the uplink, for example 4KB batches of data every 20ms, tolerating a maximum jitter of 5 ms. In the downlink control commands are transmitted every 10 ms.

4.3.5. Summary of manufacturing requirements from State of the Art

Based on the surveyed use cases, we conclude this section providing a rough categorization of the identified use cases, and identifying the main functional requirements derived from these categories from a communication perspective.

Table 4-2. Summary of state of the art use cases and requirements

Category	Description	Main connectivity functional requirements
Control to Control	Including communication between PLCs, or communication between PLCs and control functions deployed in the factory edge	Seamless integration Ethernet TSN and wireless segments Bounded latency of (small) message delivery
Offloading / remote operation	Featuring offloading a compute intensive capability currently embedded within a device or production line to a remote location	High uplink capacity, including supplementary video transmissions. Deterministic communication service for downlink control loop
Positioning	Including use cases where an edge-based service needs to track in real-time the position of a mobile robot or AGV.	Increase anchor coverage, to reduce number of required anchors. Reliable sub-meter precision.

5. 6GSMART Reference Use Cases: Requirements, Key enablers and preliminary architecture

In this section we present a selection of three manufacturing use cases, which will be used to drive the design of the 6G enablers for manufacturing developed in the 6GSMART project.

5.1. Use Case #1: AI enabled quality Control

5.1.1. Use Case description

5.1.1.1. *Motivation*

This use case consists of the implementation AI vision algorithms applied to real-time defect detection in manufacturing environments.

Defect detection is implemented nowadays mostly as a manual process, whereby batches of manufactured parts are analyzed in the laboratory to assess the level of quality of the production process. Note that production processes tend to degrade over time, thus periodic offline quality assessments allow to detect if the process is deviating from the expected quality. However, this offline approach only provides statistical guarantees, and it makes it impossible to ensure that 100% of the manufactured parts are defect free.

Adopting AI vision methods for defect control is a disruptive approach to defect detection. Namely, by installing AI powered cameras at the end of the production line, each individual manufactured part can be assessed in real time. The challenge is to minimize the cost of installing the AI vision cameras, and to be able to execute the AI processing within the time budget allocated by the production process, which for typical production processes at BOSCH Aranjuez is in the order of several seconds.

5.1.1.2. *Current implementation*

Currently, BOSCH Aranjuez employs localized PLCs/IPC's for the implementation of AI vision systems. These PLCs are collocated directly at the individual workstations as described in Figure 6: Current configuration for AI based defect control systems, operating within two specific lines: the AC-Interface line and the Heater Membrane line.

Figure 6: Current configuration for AI based defect control systems. Same architecture is replicated in each production line

To manage real-time image processing, these PLCs are designed for high performance, capable of executing complex algorithms and to deliver timely responses. Thus, the current architecture increases operational costs due to the necessity of several high-end devices. Notice that these high-end devices would need to be deployed at each production line integrating AI vision defect control.

An example of the current implementation is the AI based visual control for the EVO membrane product. As depicted in Figure 7, the EVO membrane is small and has a complex shape. Because of this shape and the special plastic used to produce it, some gas problems arise within the mold in the injection process, which may generate rugosity in the piece, resulting in defects. Figure 8 depicts the main scrap defects appearing the in EVO membrane, and Figure 9 provides examples of additional defects.

Figure 7: Shape of EVO Membrane

Figure 8: Main SCRAP reasons

Figure 9: Other SCRAP reasons

To be able to detect all this variety of defects in real-time, BOSCH Aranjuez has designed a system that creates stereoscopic images with 2 cameras and 8 flash-lights, and a third camera that checks other defects on the part. The 3D design of the AI vision system with the three cameras is depicted in Figure 10: Layout of the AI vision defect control for the heater membrane production line. Hence, for each manufactured part, the three described cameras take several pictures which are processed using AI algorithms that can detect the rugosity in the parts and classify the part as defect in real-time.

Figure 10: Layout of the AI vision defect control for the heater membrane production line

5.1.1.3. Future Implementation

The key design concept to drive cost down in this use case, is to centralize the AI vision hardware so that it can be shared across different production lines, which will only contain the cameras. Hence, a high-speed network is required to connect in real-time the cameras in the production line with the centralized AI vision resource pool.

For this project, BOSCH Aranjuez considers the integration of two specific artificial vision systems into a centralized high-performance server: 1) AC-Interface production line, and 2) Heater Membrane production line. The centralized server will be tasked with real-time processing of complex artificial vision algorithms.

The connection between the workstations and the central server will be facilitated via a dedicated 5G network as showed on the Figure 11: Envisioned architecture for AI vision defect control use case. Note that the current Ethernet network used for PLC to MES communications cannot be used to transport the AI vision traffic. The reason is that PLC-MES communications are critical, and therefore need to be isolated from the AI vision traffic. Thus, a parallel network needs to be deployed for the AI vision traffic, and a dedicate private 5G network is the most economic way of implementing this dedicated network.

A dedicated private 5G network will also allow for the seamless transmission of images to a separate database for archival and further analysis. This configuration will also enable BOSCH to configure and modify the software directly from the server, avoiding the physical connection in the line and being able to modify the centralized software only once.

Figure 11: Envisioned architecture for AI vision defect control use case

5.1.2. Requirements: Functional and Non-Functional

We discuss in this section the main functional and non-functional requirements derived from this use case.

Table 5-1. UC1 functional and non-functional requirements

Functional Requirements	
UC1-FR1	The designed solution should be scalable, so that the system allows for future expansion to include all visual inspection stations in the plant.
UC1-FR2	The designed solution must operate within the existing production line's cycle time to ensure no negative impact on efficiency.
UC1-FR3	The designed network solution should allow to connect production lines located in different shopfloors. Fiber connectivity between shopfloors may be considered, but a wireless solution is preferable
UC1-FR4	The designed network should be isolated, because the AI vision network traffic cannot interfere with the existing plant communication lines.
Non-functional requirements	
UC1-NFR1	Service level latency should be below 100 ms, where service latency is defined as the latency between the time the image is taken in the production line and the time the image is available in the centralized server for processing.
UC1-NFR2	The product cycle time is 7 seconds. Therefore, the AI vision system and the designed network should be designed such that a defect or no defect decision can be taken within the product cycle time.
UC1-NFR3	The designed system should be able to transmit at least 10 images of 80MB for each cycle time.

5.1.3. Key 6G enabling technologies

Based on the functional and non-functional requirements identified in the previous sections, we identify the following communication challenges associated with this use case:

- Extremely high uplink and area capacities. A production line generating 10 images of 80MB each, for a manufacturing process time of 5 seconds would require a dedicated 1.28 Gbps of uplink capacity. If ten production lines are active in the same factory floor, a total of 12.80 Gbps of AI-vision related uplink traffic would have to be supported.
- Connecting distributed factory floors. As described in the previous sections, a typical manufacturing facility consists of multiple factory floors, where each factory floor includes several (e.g. tens) production lines, and each production line may include an AI-vision based defect detection system. To provide dedicated wireless capacity in each factory floor, it is required to deploy indoor antennas. However, for costs reasons, a single dedicate private 5G core network should be deployed for the whole factory, which requires to have an effective way of

connecting 5G cells distributed across different factory floors to a common 5G core, taking into consideration the costs required to lay out dedicate fibers.

Looking at the previous requirements, the following 6GSMART network technologies are seen as promising enablers for this use case:

- *Industrial cloud continuum*: The proposed use case includes processing in the private edge of the factory, and, optionally, processing in a lightweight computer element co-located with the production line being monitored. The purpose of the lightweight compute can be for example to compress the camera images before being transmitted, thus substantially reducing the uplink transmission requirements. Cloud continuum challenges appearing in this use case include:
 - Ability to configure the compression-related jobs executed in the lightweight compute according to the specific manufacturing process being considered.
 - Ability to virtualize and flexibly allocate GPU capacity from the private factory edge across all the vision-related workloads coming from the production lines in the factory. Notice that AI-vision compute requirements coming from each production line may significantly diverge, as the AI-vision application needs to be customized to each specific manufacturing process.
- *Uplink capacity enhancements through RAT aggregation*: The main feature of this use case is the extreme uplink bandwidth required. Considering that a single midband 5G cell of 100 MHz and a MIMO 2x2 configuration, could provide around 500 Mbps of uplink capacity for the whole factory floor [12], aggregating multiple carriers is a must to be able to meet the use case requirements. Carrier aggregation can be considered within 3GPP by aggregating FR1 and FR2 cells using dual connectivity, or across 3GPP and Wi-Fi systems by means of Adaptive Traffic Steering Splitting and Switching (ATSSS). Such implementations are susceptible to the dynamic environment of the factory floor. Unintended interferences or reflections caused by temporary obstacles (e.g. big material boxes, forklifts) might compromise the use case requirements. For this reason, an ad-hoc fleet of AGVs with 5G/6G capabilities will be deployed to assess network quality at each production line when required by each manufacturing process cycle. For those cases where the signal quality is not enough to satisfy the use case requirements, as a second step, the set of AGVs will be coordinated to be placed at the specific locations that enhance the uplink capacity of the production lines, thus allowing their requirements to be met. Optimal performance of this implementation would also require an accurate localization of the AGVs within the factory. Efficient implementations of these mechanisms are required to achieve the target use case uplink capacity.
- *TSN enabled fronthaul*: To achieve the required uplink capacity multiple cells in the factory floor will have to be deployed, especially in the case of FR2 cells. These cells require to be time synchronized to operate, but GNSS is generally not available inside the factory floor. This requires a TSN-enabled fronthaul segment that can be used to distribute clock signals across distributed factory floors. The TSN enabled fronthaul may be used as well to provide transport performance

guarantees to the fronthaul or midhaul traffic flows, which will depend on the deployed 5G RAN architecture in the factory. The TSN fronthaul/midhaul network can also be used to connect the factory floors to the location where the CU functions and the core network are located. Being the factory floors distributed, a high-capacity wireless backhaul would be convenient, e.g., based on Sub-THz wireless links.

- Application aware network optimization through enhanced NaaS APIs: A relevant feature of this use case is that the application pattern resulting from different AI-vision applications running in the same factory floor is completely predictable. Each production line operates under a well-known process time, within which the instants when the cameras capture images and the instants when these images need to be transmitted through the network can be known in advance. Making the network aware of this application pattern through enhanced NaaS APIs could be used to optimize the underlying network performance. For example, assuming that each production line is connected to a CPE that embeds a UE function, the MAC scheduling function within a DU could associate each UE to a given deadline of the manufacturing process, thereby enabling a sort of application-layer earliest deadline first scheduling that would prioritize the transmission of AI-vision images where the manufacturing process is running closer to the process deadline.

5.1.4. Preliminary UC design and architecture

Figure 12 provides a high-level deployment architecture for this use case that includes the 6GSMART technologies identified in the previous section.

The proposed architecture consists of a distributed set of factory floors in the manufacturing facility, i.e., factory floor #1 to factory floor #N. The exterior structure of each factory floor is typically covered with a metallic sheet, which hinders propagation conditions from antennas located outside the factory floor. Therefore, the proposed design includes a set of 5G/6G cells, both in FR1 and FR2 bands, located inside each factory floor, alongside Wi-Fi access points operating in the 6GHZ band.

Each factory floor includes a set of production lines that feature AI-vision systems. Each production line is equipped with a set of high-resolution cameras for the AI-vision system, an extreme edge computing device, which can for example apply compression techniques locally, and a multi-RAT CPE device, which is able to connect to the multiple 5G/6G cells and Wi-Fi APs available in the factory floor. Furthermore, each factory floor is equipped by a fleet or AGVs with 5G/6G capabilities to map the radio quality and, when required, enhance the radio signal.

A single factory floor is selected to host the CU component of the 5G RAN, as well as the 5GCore network components. This factory floor also hosts the application servers that will be used to implement the centralized GPU enabled cluster for AI-vision applications. It is therefore necessary to deploy a transport network connecting all factory floors to the factory floor hosting the CU and the core network. TSN can be used to implement this network segment, preferably operating over wireless links across factory floors, to avoid having to lay out new fiber connections. Such point-to-point TSN enabled wireless links could be based on Sub-THz wireless technologies supporting enhanced capacities. The

TSN network can also be used to propagate a master clock signal, obtained from a GNSS receiver deployed outdoors, to all the DU functions deployed across the different factory floors.

Finally, although not explicitly depicted in Figure 12, application specific patterns could be provisioned through the Network Exposure Function (NEF) of the 5GCore, which would then propagate this information to the relevant network functions using the core network control plane.

Figure 12. Proposed deployment architecture for UC1 integrating 6GSMART networking enablers.

5.2. Use Case #2: High precision metrology

5.2.1. Use Case description

5.2.1.1. Motivation

According to the recent definition made by the European Commission regarding “Industry 5.0”, it attempts to capture the value of new technologies, providing prosperity beyond jobs and growth, while respecting planetary boundaries, and placing the wellbeing of the industry worker at the center of the production process. This means a transition towards a **sustainable, human-centric and resilient industry**.

While talking about *sustainable manufacturing*, relevant processes such as energy consumption, environment impact or manufacturing cost need to be considered. By improving the performance of production methods and operations, we can also upgrade the quality control that is attached to the manufacturing process, and in the end, reduce the number of production steps, minimizing the energy use that is needed, or material waste.

This is not only related to the correct design of the manufacturing process since the very beginning, but also to the digitalization strategy that is applied. In this regard, resilience in the manufacturing industry is aimed to provide the possibility to **anticipate, react and learn** timely and systematically from any crisis (or unplanned events) and thereby **ensure** stable and sustainable **performance**. As depicted in Figure 13, from the individual level of the manufacturing process to the plant or even industrial sector level, resilience is a capability built upon:

- *Preparedness*: In order to provide a proper response to any event, the work force needs to know what to expect regarding the environment, the machinery and the process itself. Anticipating is the key.
- *Awareness*: Different manufacturing processes need different monitoring tools, but a close follow-up needs to be performed over the key indicators to provide efficient monitoring. Knowledge about the specific manufacturing process leads to a well-designed monitoring system.
- *Intelligence*: When the information about the performance during the manufacturing process is gathered, and even more nowadays that great amount of quality data can be retrieved, the logical step is to identify the deviations or warnings by analyzing the indicators from the monitoring system. Pointing put what to do based on smart/artificial intelligence solutions once again paths the way to increase the efficiency of the manufacturing process.
- *Value Creation*: Resilience is not a linear process but a cyclic one, where the entire activities involved in the manufacturing process have to be evaluated, from the preparedness to the response, to stablish a continuous learning plan that will contribute to the continuous improvement of both the process and the workforce.

Figure 13. Resilience in the manufacturing industry

On the other hand, and in order to address the challenges that manufacturing is facing when dealing with Globalization, it is highly remarkable the Human-Centric approach, that enables manufacturing organizations to match and fulfil customers' individual product requirements with highly automated production, highest levels of quality and low time investment. To meet the current and future needs of this customized form of fabrication resulting from globalization, innovative and cutting-edge technologies and solutions like 6G are needed.

However, the traditional approach towards the digitalization of industry that nowadays has its starting point in the mapping of the manufacturing processes and then implementing digital solutions for the monitoring or automatization of those processes is no longer the solution. A **new Transformational approach** needs to be implemented to ensure a successful digitalization of the industry. As a result, first of all, a mapping of the digital processes must be performed in order to lately transfer them to the physical world.

In the Industry 5.0 scenario, **metrology** is facing similar challenges. Companies dedicated to manufacturing parts and components for key sectors such as the automotive, aeronautical, energy, etc. are receiving dimensional quality requirements and tolerances from large companies. To achieve the compliance level in terms of quality control, metrology is the key.

Currently, the metrological process for quality control measurement systems has an associated information processing software that can be parameterized. However, measurements are performed at the end of the manufacturing process (EoL or End of Line inspection) and mostly off-line in dedicated metrology rooms to ensure the correct environment (in terms of light and temperature) for accurate results. In addition, these metrological laboratories lack equipment control, operation, monitoring and sensors, that have been pointed out as enabling elements for a successful digitalization.

As depicted in Figure 14, considering the new Human Centric approach to the digitalization of the manufacturing process, and applying resilient concepts such as preparedness, awareness and intelligence, metrology can transform and digitalize its main

processes with the use of advanced computing techniques (both cloud and edge) and 6G connectivity.

Figure 14. Resilient and Human Centric approach to digitalization.

The human centric and resilient approach to the digitalization of metrology using 6G connectivity, will be tested and validated in this Pilot while providing the capacity to configure and operate a CMM (Coordinate Measuring Machine) remotely, that will result in:

- More agile in-line quality control process
- A relevant contribution to the digitalization of the manufacturing process
- Easily adjusting to changes or unplanned events during production
- Reducing the time spent in calibration or maintenance operations.
- Increasing the measurements that can be performed without errors and so, the number of customers.

5.2.1.2. Current implementation

The current scenario in dimensional metrology is mainly made up of measuring machines (e.g. Vulcan System by TRIMEK in this particular use case) and metrology software (M3 Platform in this use case)

Figure 15. Traditional alignment of a CMM

The Metrological machine that will be utilized in 6GSMART, the Vulcan System, is a horizontal arm with high stiffness structure to ensure accuracy and compatible with optical scanning and feeler accessories (see Figure 16).

Figure 16. *Vulcan System for Metrological analysis*

M3 is a high-performance software for capturing and analysing clouds of online automatic scanning points for reliable and efficient acquisition of 3D information for different materials. It consists of M3 Gages, M3 Server and M3 Tablet (<http://m3.innovalia-metrology.com/>).

- M3 Gage is the complete 3D capture integration system, capable of working with different types of sensors and components.
- M3 Server provides a solution for highly efficient, secure, and flexible management of virtual part information for mass 3D point cloud storage.
- M3 Tablet provides a workstation solution for mobile and portable virtual metrology, for convenient digital analysis of 3D measurements information and the evaluation of the production process.

The traditional metrological process, as shown in Figure 17 consists of 7 main steps:

1. When focusing on what is going to be measured, the starting point is the CAD file of the part. In this step the dimension and tolerances to be measured are analyzed in order to identify which machine and technology is the best to do the measurements.
2. The geometry and dimension tolerances are defined, and the quality information framework is created. This step consists of transferring the dimensional information from the CAD to the M3 software measurement design program. This is the beginning of the measuring process.
3. At this point, the metrologists design a measurement plan. The points to be measured are identified and the external conditions for the measurement are chosen. For instance, the metrologist chooses the exposure time or the scan direction density in case an optical scanner is being used.

4. Machine programming: definition of the trajectory (the travel of the arm of the Vulcan machine)
5. A trajectory simulation is performed aimed at detecting errors in the previous program.
6. The machine performs the final measurement, and so, the point cloud that afterwards is analyzed through the M3 software is obtained.
7. The results of the measurement are obtained as a report (that can also be a digital report) that offers different types of visualization options such as color mapping plot. In case the results are not accurate, the process must be repeated.

Figure 17. Current Measurement Process

This entire measurement process can nowadays be performed with a remote desktop, that allows the remote performance of certain steps of the process, but it does not provide the possibility to actually operate remotely the machine, or to execute any action that has not been integrated in the measuring plan and programming. Figure 18 depicts the currently available remote desktop operation.

Figure 18. Metrological Current scenario

The following gaps exist in the current implementation:

- *Remote configuration of inline and CMM equipment:* The current process requires the physical presence of a metrologist next to the CMM and the m3 software workstation to execute any additional configuration when needed.

- *Remote programming of quality control routines:* The current process does not allow to perform any quality control that is not programmed at the m3 workstation next to the CMM.
- *Predictive maintenance through machine feedback.* No relevant information regarding the performance of the CMM during the measurement process is retrieved and so, the implementation of predictive maintenance to avoid or reduce errors is not a current possibility.
- *Real time monitoring for measurement planning adaptation to alerts and errors:* A low level of monitoring is available in the CMM and it always needs the presence of a technician next to the working station.
- *Optimization of the digital program over the physical measurement machine (alignments, trajectory, part positioning):* While a measuring program can be sent remotely to the current CMM, it cannot be adapted or optimized remotely taking into account the part positioning or alignment. Once again, the presence of a technician at the working station is needed.
- *Edge powered 3D point cloud processing and analysis.* While measuring certain parts, particularly those with complex geometries, the point cloud that is analyzed to obtain the final report of the measurements is usually very heavy. The current process does not allow to process this type of “big” point clouds near to where it has been captured. It needs to be transferred to the main working station for its processing and final analysis.

5.2.1.3. Future Implementation

As depicted in Figure 19 and in order to fill the previously identified gaps in the remote metrological process shown in chapter 5.2.1.2., the implementation of 5G/6G connectivity will provide:

- **Wireless connectivity** for metrologist to perform the measurements regardless of their location.
- **Real time monitoring and remote visualization** of the process (cameras to visualize the point that is being measured in detail as well as the complete part)
- **Remotely controlling and operating** the CMM in response of any event, expected or not.
- **Predictive maintenance** through sensors hub and monitoring
- Advanced management of the measurement process lifecycle.

Figure 19. Future Implementation Diagram

5.2.2. Requirements: Functional and Non-Functional

We discuss in this section the main functional and non-functional requirements derived from this use case.

Table 5-2. UC2 functional and non-functional requirements

Functional Requirements	
UC2-FR1	<p>The solution shall allow the operator to control the quality control equipment remotely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The solution shall allow the operator to remotely control the movement (position and speed) of the quality control equipment's axis (and the integrated sensing tool). - The solution shall allow the operator to remotely control the configuration and operation of the sensing tool (optical laser sensor) - The solution shall allow the operator to receive the position of the sensing tool (or/and the 3D points scanned by the sensing tool)
UC2-FR2	<p>The solution shall give the operator access to real-time video captured in the quality control lab by full-HD cameras:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The solution shall allow the operator to change between full-HD and low-resolution cameras configuration. - The solution shall allow the operator to select the camera to visualize / to choose both or individual cameras visualization.
UC2-FR3	<p>The solution shall allow the monitoring of the quality control systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The solution shall give the operator access to sensors data monitoring quality control equipment systems (air pressure, energy consumption, linear and rotary axis alarm events, control lab, CMM and piece temperatures, etc.) - The solution shall allow the operator to adjust sensors data monitoring frequency.
UC2-FR4	<p>The solution shall allow the operator to prioritize traffic for each service (remote control, remote visualization and system monitoring):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The solution shall allow to establish rules to adjust the traffic priority of the services based on 4 levels (critical, severe, alarm, warning)
Non-functional requirements	
UC2-NFR1	<p>The 5G/6G network shall be stable enough to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guarantee continuous operation. - Enable safety of operation: quick reaction to alarms and events
UC2-NFR2	<p>The 5G/6G network shall allow to prioritize traffic according to the stakeholder's criteria.</p>
UC2-NFR3	<p>Packets loss should be zero. Reliable transport protocols should be used.</p>
UC2-NFR4	<p>Latency should be under 12-14 ms for remote control of the equipment</p>
UC2-NFR5	<p>Transfer rate should be able to transmit Full-HD video for real-time video.</p>

UC2-NFR6	Transfer rate shall be able to transmit video, position coordinates of a set of points, sensors measurement dataset (air pressure levels in 3 axis, electric current/power, 3 linear and 2 rotary axis positions, room, CMM and piece temperatures, ...).
UC2-NFR7	Traffic data related to the sensing tool position shall include a time-stamp to ensure data reception order is not altered.
UC2-NFR8	A switch should be used to give access to RobotLink, Sensors Hub and Remote Cameras services/modules to a 5G CPE.
UC2-NFR9	Latency lower than 4 ms for the transmission of critical data

5.2.3. Key 6G enabling technologies

The connected metrology system in 6GSMART will enable the M3 software stack with remote machine control, remote visual access, and remote machine monitoring capabilities. This requires the wireless transmission of a set of data streams:

- Control/position information from the controller in the CMM and RobotLink.
- Data from remote cameras.
- Data from monitoring sensors and the Sensors Hub.

Based on the functional and non-functional requirements identified in the previous sections, we identify the following communication challenges associated with this use case:

- Extremely low latencies. Critical control data in this use case should ideally be transmitted with latencies lower than 4 ms, on both the uplink and the downlink. Since such ultra-low latency is not achievable in a practical setting, one of the focus of validations will be to test the lowest feasible latency in a practical deployment scenario, and its applicability to the transmission of control signals. Moreover, other non-critical, non-control data streams also need to be transmitted through the 5G network.
- Remote connection to production room. This use case will enable a more agile quality control process, through two key components: (i) remote operation of quality control equipment by connected workers, and (ii) an augmented zero-defect manufacturing (ZDM) decision support system for connected workers. Connected workers are expected to work in a dedicated space physically separated from the production floor, where they can remotely oversee and control the quality of the pieces being produced using a specially designed software tool. To enable remote quality control, it is necessary to deploy the remote-control applications on a 5G-enabled device, which shall connect to the services running on the production area through a public network.
- Reconfigurability and modularity. 5G can enable the modularity and reconfigurability of the production process, by providing connectivity to various elements of the use case. Taking into consideration the intricacies of the production process and the layout of industrial facilities, a pivotal decision must be made regarding which specific building blocks of the use case should be mobile

and which should be fixed. This decision will ultimately define the architecture and layout of the 5G network components.

Looking at the previous requirements, the following 6GSMART network technologies are seen as promising enablers for this use case:

- *Industrial cloud continuum*: The proposed use case includes distributed processing and application elements, both in the industrial edge, co-located to the industrial machinery (robotic arm); and in the remote quality control office where the production process is monitored. The software components running in the industrial edge are three: (i) the RobotLink, (ii) Remote Cameras, and (iii) Sensors Hub. The current application software stack is mainly monolithic, with a tight integration between functions and components, and where the main challenge is related to the provisioning of the necessary networking and connectivity. However, the use case could benefit from the application of a cloud-native architectural style based on microservices. This could bring enhanced functionalities, for example, the ability to perform pre-processing of camera and sensor data to reduce transmission requirements, enhanced modularity and flexibility to run application components in off-the-shelf computing units with enhanced capabilities, enhanced flexibility in performing software upgrades in a non-disruptive manner, and so on. Related cloud-continuum challenges include:
 - Need to containerize the production process application stack to run in cloud-native environments.
 - Security aspects related to the containerization of certain components, e.g., those that perform low-level actions over hardware interfaces, which need to be carefully balanced when containerizing the application, striking the right balance between flexibility and security.
 - Increased time lag introduced by the addition of an abstraction layer in cloud-native environments, which might impact the applicability of microservice-based architectures to scenarios with very strict latency requirements.
 - Ability to virtualize and flexibly allocate computational resources from the industrial cloud continuum to each production application process.
- *Multiple 5G traffic priorities*: one of the key non-functional requirements of the use case is that traffic should be prioritized according to some stakeholder criteria. For example, control signaling has the most stringent requirements in terms of latency, cyclicality, and packet loss. In contrast, camera and sensor data are not so critical for the production process. Such traffic prioritization can be achieved through the use of QoS Class Identifiers (QCI) in 5G and, potentially, through the use of network slicing, where a network slice with a specific QCI is dedicated to the transmission of one type of data only.
- *Radio capacity enhancements through RAT aggregation*: Critical control data in this use case needs to be transmitted with latency and packet loss guarantees. This challenge can be partially addressed through the use of carrier aggregation, for example across 3GPP and Wi-Fi systems by means of Adaptive Traffic Steering Splitting and Switching (ATSSS), which would enhance reliability and reduce latency by transmitting critical data in parallel through both RATs.

- Service delivery through public 5G network: The requirement to use public networks in this use case requires a well-planned integration between the on-premises IT/OT networks and the public network, as well as certain degree of controllability over the use of the required network resources. In this regard, the use of CAMARA APIs by the mobile network provider (MNO) provides a suitable mechanism for the use case owner to request public resources, for example through the use of a quality on demand (QoD) API for the provisioning of network resources (or network slices) with given quality guarantees [13].

5.2.4. Preliminary UC design and architecture

Figure 20 provides a high-level deployment architecture for this use case that includes the 6GSMART technologies identified in the previous section.

The proposed architecture consists of a physically separated production room (where the CMM and the extreme edge are co-located) and remote-control room (where the private edge is located) which, in Figure 20, are represented as two separate production domains. The production room includes a metrology robot that performs agile in-line quality control, as well as several cameras and monitoring sensors; a controller sends control data to the RobotLink, which is also transmitted to the remote machine control application on the telco edge. Remote camera data is transmitted to the private edge for remote visual access, while monitoring sensor data is transmitted to the private edge to support remote machine monitoring.

The remote-control room includes a setup for connected worker remote operation and for connected worker augmented ZDM decision support system, as well as the necessary application modules to analyze camera and sensor data.

The proposed design leverages the use of 5G/6G network resources exposed by a public network. A 5G-enabled device, where the remote M3 software components can run, is also used for providing 5G connectivity to the production area. In addition, an orchestration system provides the management of resources across the industrial compute continuum, including the extreme edge and the public network. Such orchestration system runs in the telco edge.

In Figure 20, both production domains are connected to the on-premise IT domain through a gateway and, in turn, the IT domain connects to the public network through another gateway. The public network exposes available resources through a CAMARA API; in the use case, this is leveraged for the provisioning of QoD network resources.

Figure 20: Proposed deployment architecture for UC2 integrating 6GSMART cloud continuum and networking enablers.

5.3. Use Case #3: XR enabled remote assistance

5.3.1. Use Case description

5.3.1.1. Motivation

Remote teleassistance, often referred to simply as teleassistance, is a service or technology that allows individuals or organizations to provide assistance and support to others from a remote location, typically using telecommunications and digital technologies. It has become increasingly important with the need for remote services in various industries. It plays a significant role in enhancing access to expertise, support, and services, especially in situations where physical presence is challenging.

In the not-so-distant future, the world of communication and collaboration is set to undergo a profound transformation, ushering in a new era of connectivity and interaction. Imagine a world where you can converse with a friend or colleague, not through a two-dimensional screen, but as a vivid, three-dimensional environment.

In such an environment, real-time shared collaboration will be crucially enhanced. Whether it's assembling a 3D model, co-designing an interactive project, or comparing 3D models, the immersive environment will provide an improved remote assistance experience. Additionally, thanks to the integration of volumetric communications between humans (holoportation or holoconferencing), the human nature of communication between people will be preserved, thanks to the possibility of representing body language, natural movement and natural manipulation of objects.

Figure 21. The past, present and future of video-conferencing. From 2D mosaicking towards virtual meetings, initially with avatars and then with real humans represented as volumetric video

5.3.1.2. Current implementation

Non-immersive solutions are practical for standard videoconferencing scenarios, with limitations such as capturing non-verbal communication and achieving full replication of real-life operations. In particular, the following can be summarized:

- **GAP1 - Lack of immersiveness:** Traditional videoconferencing solutions lack the immersive quality of AR and VR, making it challenging to replicate the feeling of physically being in the same environment.
- **GAP2 - Remote Assistance relying only on audio and 2D video:** These solutions primarily rely on audio and 2D video, limiting the depth and quality of interactions.
- **GAP3 - Lack of non-verbal communication:** Non-immersive applications struggle to capture and convey non-verbal cues and gestures, which are crucial for effective communication.
- **GAP4 - Lack of real-life operations examples:** The absence of 3D models and simulations makes it difficult to provide real-life, interactive demonstrations or training.

On the other hand, the evolving landscape of remote communication technologies continues to bridge these gaps and offer more versatile solutions for various industries and use cases, such as availability of 3D models for simulations and immersiveness for the worker. However, with still some limitations, such as lack of non-verbal communication, remote assistance is still based on 2D video and lacks of real-life operations examples.

Figure 22. Example usage scenarios of holoportation technology

5.3.1.3. Future Implementation

The proposed Use Case will solve the previous gaps by providing the following features:

- **Multuser interaction and collaboration in XR:** Providing benefits in terms of realism, naturalness, comfort, plausibility, while agile access and safety.
- **Remote assistance from worldwide experts:** Allowing full body gestures, and non-verbal expressions.
- **Interactivity and realistic actions:** Such as 3D inspection, manipulation of environments, interaction with 3D assets and elements.

Figure 23 depicts how future 5G/6G networks can be used to support holoportation technology. We can see how several functions of the holoportation service can be hosted either in the public cloud (e.g. the orchestrator or media server components), whereas more time critical components can be hosted in the telco edge (e.g. the communication managers). On the client side, we have the capture system and the Head Mounted Display (HMD), which may connect to a public 5G/6G network, either directly or through a CPE, which could be typically integrated within a home gateway.

Figure 23. Vision of holographic communications supported by 5G/6G networks

5.3.2. Requirements: Functional and Non-Functional

We discuss in this section the main functional and non-functional requirements derived from this use case.

Table 5-3. UC3 functional and non-functional requirements

Code	Requirement		
UC3-FR1	The solution shall enable volumetric Holographic representation of remotely located users		
UC3-FR2	The solution shall support real-time audiovisual communications		
UC3-FR3	The solution shall be of easy to integrate within a shared VR environment		
UC3-FR4	The solution shall support multiuser interaction / collaboration features		
UC3-FR5	The solution shall provide support for VR mode (VR headset) and non-VR mode (2D screens)		
UC3-FR6	The solution shall enable edge based VNF If the deployment is performed on a private network		
Non-functional requirements			
Code	Component	Uplink/ Downlink	Requirement
UC3-NFR1	Client	Uplink/ Downlink	The holoconferencing platform shall support at least 2 remote tele-ported users

UC3-NFR2	Network	Uplink/Downlink	The end-to-end delays for audiovisual communications shall be ≤ 200 ms
UC3-NFR3	Client	Uplink/Downlink	The virtual shared environment shall support at least 3 interaction modalities
UC3-NFR4	Network	Uplink/Downlink	The virtual shared environment shall provide interaction with delay, and thus sync error, ≤ 100 ms for event/interaction
UC3-NFR5	Capturing System	Uplink	The holoconferencing platform shall enable volumetric Video Streams with frame rate ≥ 15 fps
UC3-NFR6	Capturing System	Uplink	The holoconferencing platform shall enable volumetric Video Streams with resolution ≥ 100 K voxels/frame
UC3-NFR7	Compression System	Uplink	The holoconferencing platform shall enable volumetric Video Streams with bandwidth < 50 Mbps / user

5.3.3. Key 6G enabling technologies

Based on the previous functional and non-functional requirements, we identify the following 6GSMART networking enablers as relevant for this use case:

- Industrial Cloud Continuum: Holographic communication is a computationally intensive service. This high computational requirement leads to bulky and power-hungry end user devices, for example in the case of Head Mounted Display (HMDs). To simplify end-user devices is necessary to offload some of the computational function towards the network, for example to the Telco Edge Cloud (i.e. edge resources available in the public network). Thus, one can envision computational resources embedded in the XR end user devices (HMD and capture systems), which we refer to as extreme edge functions, along with computational resources in the public network, which we refer to as the Telco edge domain. Additional media related functions that do not have real-time requirements could also be hosted in public cloud resources. Thus, this service includes a continuum of computational resources, i.e. device – telco – cloud, which needs to be orchestrated efficiently for an optimal service performance.
- Enhanced wireless capacities: Holographic communications are bandwidth hungry both in uplink, where the capture system streams the 3D point clouds, and downlink, where the point clouds of the rest of the session participants are delivered to the HMD. As captured in the UC requirements, up to 50 Mbps per user may be required, which can easily lead to congestion in current public network. Notice that connection through the public network is a requirement in this use case, since the expert and the factory floor may be located in very distant locations. Considering that holographic communications is a service that will be mostly consumed indoors, a 6GSMART technology that can contribute to enhancing the capacity of wireless interface is WiFi/5G NR aggregation. Based on the Adaptive Traffic Steering, Switching and Splitting (ATSSS) technology

standardized in 3GPP [9], capacity of the public 5G network could be aggregated with capacity of an indoor Wi-Fi network, considering WiFi+5G capable end user devices.

- TSN capabilities: Media functions require synchronization, for example to align 3D clouds coming from different sources to the same media frame. Therefore, it is of interest to be able to serve a common time reference from the network to the different media functions, both functions located in the extreme edge or in the telco edge. Time Sensitive Networking capabilities can be used to propagate a master clock located in the network domain towards the end user devices.
- Network capability exposure: Exposure of network capabilities through the Network Exposure Function (NEF) of the 5GCore, or through higher level middleware such as CAMARA [13], are very relevant to provide reliable holographic communications. For example, upon detecting a degradation in the media quality a media function could request the public network for a quality boost using the CAMARA Quality on Demand (QoD) API.

5.3.4. Preliminary UC design and architecture

Figure 24 brings together the 6G networking enablers and the UC3 service components. We can see in the figure how the remote expert and the worker in the factory floor communicate through a public 5G/6G network.

Figure 24 highlights the cloud continuum aspects of UC3, with compute functions embedded in the HMD and capture devices, as well as in the Telco edge. Enhanced wireless capacities are achieved by aggregating the indoor Wi-Fi links with the capacity offered by the public 5G network, by means of using an N3IWF function to inject WiFi originated traffic into the 5GCore, and using ATSSS to aggregate WiFi and 5G traffic into a single traffic stream. A master clock inside the public network domain is also depicted to distribute a common time source to the different media functions distributed across the network, either in the extreme edge or in the telco edge. Finally, the control plane functions of the XR application (e.g. the XR orchestrator) consume network APIs exposed by the Network Exposure Function (NEF) to optimize the quality of the media

session.

Figure 24. Envision 6GSMART architecture for UC3

6. Conclusions

To ensure adoption in the manufacturing domain 5G-Advanced and 6G technologies need to be designed considering the requirements of the Industry 5.0 since the beginning. In this deliverable we have presented three manufacturing applications that will guide the development of 5G-Advanced and 6G technologies in the 6GSMART project. These use cases include: i) Scalable real time quality control of production lines using AI vision systems, ii) remote operation of high precision metrology equipment, and iii) the use of holo-portation technologies for remote assistance applications.

For each of our guiding manufacturing services we have proposed a forward-looking view that defines how 5G-A/6G technologies can be used to enhance these services, and we have identified functional and non-functional requirements. We have also identified how the 5G-A/6G technologies considered in 6GSMART can contribute to each service, such as industrial cloud continuum, NaaS APIs, or mechanisms to enhance uplink data rates.

This deliverable will serve as basis to guide the development of 5G-A/6G technologies in the 6GSMART-EZ and 6GSMART-ICC subprojects, and to define demonstrators and PoCs in the 6GSMART-EXP subproject.

7. References

- [1] 5G-ACIA, "Key 5G Use Cases and Requirements," 2020.
- [2] 3GPP, «TS 22.104, Service requirements for cyber-physical control applications in vertical domains,» 2023.
- [3] 5G-SMART, «<https://5gsmart.eu/>,» [En línea]. [Último acceso: 2023].
- [4] 5G-SMART, «D1.1, FORWARD LOOKING SMART MANUFACTURING USE CASES, REQUIREMENTS AND KPI'S,» 2020.
- [5] 5G-GROWTH, «<https://5growth.eu/>,» [En línea]. [Último acceso: 2023].
- [6] 5G-GROWTH, «D1.1: Business Model Design,» 2022.
- [7] 5G-CLARITY, «<https://5gclarity.com/>,» [En línea]. [Último acceso: 2023].
- [8] T. a. C.-M. D. e. Cogalan, «5G-CLARITY: 5G-Advanced Private Networks Integrating 5G NR, WiFi, and LiFi,» *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 2022.
- [9] 5G-CLARITY, «D5.2 Integration of Solutions and Validations,» 2023.
- [10] PREDICT6G, «<https://predict-6g.eu/>,» [En línea]. [Último acceso: 2023].
- [11] PREDICT6G, «D1.1 Analysis of use cases and system requirements,» 2023.
- [12] 5. calculator, «<https://5g-tools.com/5g-nr-throughput-calculator/>,» [En línea]. [Último acceso: 2023].
- [13] J. & D. F. Ordonez-Lucena, «Pathways towards network-as-a-service: the CAMARA project.,» de *ACM SIGCOMM Workshop on Network-Application Integration*, 2023.